

Simulating tripartite GHZ correlations with a local hidden-variable model

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A theoretical and numerical analysis of a GHZ-type experiment is presented, where polarization measurements on three entangled photons are modeled through a sigmoid-based threshold mechanism that violates the fair-sampling assumption. Numerical simulations examine how closely this local construction can approximate quantum correlations for GHZ tripartite states. Through setting-dependent detection efficiency, the model reproduces violations of both the Mermin and Svetlichny inequalities with statistical significance. The results describe how this local model can approximate quantum tripartite correlations and show how the detection mechanism shapes the statistical behavior of outcomes across entanglement regimes.

I. Introduction

Bell's theorem [1] establishes that quantum correlations violate the constraints imposed by local hidden-variable theories. This incompatibility was initially formulated for bipartite systems, but Greenberger, Horne, and Zeilinger [3, 4] demonstrated that multipartite entangled states exhibit stronger contradictions with local realism. Bouwmeester et al. [9] reported the first experimental observation of three-photon GHZ entanglement, while Pan et al. [5] performed the first experimental test of tripartite nonlocality using the GHZ argument, and showed that the corresponding statistical analysis is equivalent to a Mermin-type inequality for three-photon GHZ states. Subsequent experiments have achieved increasingly precise measurements of GHZ correlations, though complete loophole-free tests remain more challenging for tripartite systems than for bipartite ones.

Mermin [10] derived a four-term Bell inequality for tripartite systems, showing that local realism predicts $|M_3| \leq 2$ while quantum mechanics permits violations up to $|M_3| = 4$. Violation of the Mermin inequality excludes fully local hidden-variable theories, but remains compatible with bi-local models that permit arbitrary correlations between any two parties while maintaining locality with respect to the third party.

Svetlichny [6] introduced an inequality designed to detect genuine tripartite nonlocality irreducible to any bipartite structure. The Svetlichny inequality establishes a bound of $|S_3| \leq 4$ for bi-local models allowing arbitrary correlations between any two parties, while quantum mechanics permits violations up to $|S_3| = 4\sqrt{2}$.

The Mermin–Ardehali–Belinskii–Klyshko (MABK) inequality [10–12] is a family of Bell-type inequalities for n -particle GHZ states with a local realistic bound of 2 and a maximum quantum value of $2^{(n+1)/2}$. For $n = 2$, the MABK inequality reduces to the CHSH inequality [2] with maximum quantum value $2\sqrt{2}$, while for $n = 3$ it reduces to the Mermin inequality with maximum quantum value 4.

Cabello et al. [8] proved that the threshold detection efficiency for loophole-free tests of the n -partite Mermin inequality using n -qubit GHZ states is $\eta_{\text{crit}} = n/(2n - 2)$,

which gives $\eta_{\text{crit}} = 3/4$ for tripartite systems. Below this threshold, local hidden-variable models can reproduce the correlations required to violate the Mermin inequality.

Cabello [13] provided a proof of Bell's theorem without inequalities for both inequivalent classes of three-qubit entangled states (GHZ and W) under local operations and classical communication. This approach yields Bell inequalities that enable more conclusive experimental tests of Bell's theorem for tripartite states.

The minimum detection efficiency required to close the detection loophole in Svetlichny inequality tests has been subject to refinement over the years. Xiang et al. [14] derived a bound of $\eta_{\text{crit}} \approx 96.7\%$, while Ghosh et al. [15] reduced this bound to $\eta_{\text{crit}} \approx 88.1\%$ through numerical optimization over all possible measurement settings.

Despite theoretical advances, the behavior of local hidden-variable models that simulate quantum correlations for tripartite GHZ states has not yet been fully explored across different measurement settings.

The present work introduces a local hidden-variable model for tripartite GHZ states that includes a sigmoid-based threshold mechanism, exploiting the detection loophole, originally introduced by Pearle [7]. By violating the fair-sampling assumption through a setting-dependent detection mechanism, this model reproduces the violations of both the Mermin and Svetlichny inequalities while preserving locality.

II. Theoretical Framework

A source of three entangled photons is considered, prepared in the nonmaximally entangled $|\text{GHZ}_r\rangle$ state

$$|\text{GHZ}_r\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1+r^2}}(|000\rangle + r|111\rangle) \quad (1)$$

where $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ denote the horizontal (H) and vertical (V) polarization states respectively, and r is the entanglement parameter. For $r = \pm 1$, the state is maximally entangled.

Polarization measurements are performed on three spacelike separated photons. In the equatorial plane xy of the Bloch sphere, the measurement basis for a given

azimuthal angle ϕ is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} |\phi\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|0\rangle + e^{i\phi} |1\rangle) \\ |\phi^\perp\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|0\rangle - e^{i\phi} |1\rangle) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ represent the horizontal ($|H\rangle$) and vertical ($|V\rangle$) polarization states, respectively.

The quantum correlation for measurements along the equatorial plane predicted by quantum mechanics is

$$E_{\text{GHZ}}(\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta}, \hat{\gamma}, r) = \frac{2r}{1+r^2} \cos(\hat{\alpha} + \hat{\beta} + \hat{\gamma}) \quad (3)$$

where $\hat{\alpha} \in \{a, a'\}$, $\hat{\beta} \in \{b, b'\}$, and $\hat{\gamma} \in \{c, c'\}$ are the azimuthal angles in the equatorial plane for the first, second, and third photon respectively.

The state of each photon triplet is modeled with hidden-variable vectors $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$. For each triplet, an array of n samples $\{\epsilon_i\}_{i=1}^n$ is drawn from the Gaussian distribution $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_G^2)$, where $\sigma_G = |1-r^2|/(\sqrt{3}(1+r^2))$. The hidden-variable components are then constructed as

$$\lambda_k^{(i)} = \theta_k + \epsilon_i, \quad i \in \{1, \dots, n\}, \quad k \in \{1, 2, 3\} \quad (4)$$

where the means θ_k satisfy the constraint

$$\theta_1 + \theta_2 + \theta_3 = 0 \pmod{2\pi} \quad (5)$$

which is implemented by drawing $\theta_1, \theta_2 \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 2\pi)$ and setting $\theta_3 = -(\theta_1 + \theta_2) \pmod{2\pi}$.

Given the measurement angles $\hat{\alpha}$, $\hat{\beta}$, and $\hat{\gamma}$, the cumulative measurement scores (c_1^+, c_1^-) , (c_2^+, c_2^-) , and (c_3^+, c_3^-) are calculated for the first, second, and third photon respectively as

$$\begin{aligned} c_1^+ &= \sum_{i=1}^n \hat{\mathcal{H}} \left(\frac{1 + E_{\text{GHZ}}(\hat{\alpha}, \lambda_2^{(i)}, \lambda_3^{(i)}, r)}{2} - u_i \right) \times \\ &\times (1 + E_{\text{GHZ}}(\hat{\alpha}, \lambda_2^{(i)}, \lambda_3^{(i)}, r)) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} c_1^- &= \sum_{i=1}^n \hat{\mathcal{H}} \left(\frac{1 - E_{\text{GHZ}}(\hat{\alpha}, \lambda_2^{(i)}, \lambda_3^{(i)}, r)}{2} - u_i \right) \times \\ &\times (1 - E_{\text{GHZ}}(\hat{\alpha}, \lambda_2^{(i)}, \lambda_3^{(i)}, r)) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} c_2^+ &= \sum_{i=1}^n \hat{\mathcal{H}} \left(\frac{1 + E_{\text{GHZ}}(\hat{\beta}, \lambda_1^{(i)}, \lambda_3^{(i)}, r)}{2} - v_i \right) \times \\ &\times (1 + E_{\text{GHZ}}(\hat{\beta}, \lambda_1^{(i)}, \lambda_3^{(i)}, r)) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} c_2^- &= \sum_{i=1}^n \hat{\mathcal{H}} \left(\frac{1 - E_{\text{GHZ}}(\hat{\beta}, \lambda_1^{(i)}, \lambda_3^{(i)}, r)}{2} - v_i \right) \times \\ &\times (1 - E_{\text{GHZ}}(\hat{\beta}, \lambda_1^{(i)}, \lambda_3^{(i)}, r)) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} c_3^+ &= \sum_{i=1}^n \hat{\mathcal{H}} \left(\frac{1 + E_{\text{GHZ}}(\hat{\gamma}, \lambda_1^{(i)}, \lambda_2^{(i)}, r)}{2} - z_i \right) \times \\ &\times (1 + E_{\text{GHZ}}(\hat{\gamma}, \lambda_1^{(i)}, \lambda_2^{(i)}, r)) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{aligned} c_3^- &= \sum_{i=1}^n \hat{\mathcal{H}} \left(\frac{1 - E_{\text{GHZ}}(\hat{\gamma}, \lambda_1^{(i)}, \lambda_2^{(i)}, r)}{2} - z_i \right) \times \\ &\times (1 - E_{\text{GHZ}}(\hat{\gamma}, \lambda_1^{(i)}, \lambda_2^{(i)}, r)) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where $\lambda_k^{(i)}$ denotes the k -th hidden variable at the i -th sampling ($i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, $k \in \{1, 2, 3\}$), u_i , v_i , and z_i are independent random numbers sampled from $\mathcal{U}(0, 1)$, and $\hat{\mathcal{H}}$ is the modified Heaviside function

$$\hat{\mathcal{H}}(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } x \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

The correlation functions $E_{\text{GHZ}}(\rho, \lambda_j^{(i)}, \lambda_k^{(i)}, r)$ in Eqs. (6)–(11) are calculated in a local context, with $\rho \in \{\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta}, \hat{\gamma}\}$ and $j, k \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ with $j \neq k$, effectively violating the fair sampling assumption through setting-dependent detection.

The normalized cumulative scores are defined as

$$\hat{c}_j^+ = \frac{c_j^+}{c_j^+ + c_j^-}, \quad j \in \{1, 2, 3\} \quad (13)$$

$$\hat{c}_j^- = \frac{c_j^-}{c_j^+ + c_j^-}, \quad j \in \{1, 2, 3\} \quad (14)$$

and the net scores are defined as

$$\Delta \hat{c}_j = \hat{c}_j^+ - \hat{c}_j^-, \quad j \in \{1, 2, 3\} \quad (15)$$

The detection probabilities P_j^+ and P_j^- for “+” and “-” outcomes are defined with sigmoid functions

$$P_j^+ = \frac{1}{1 + \exp[-s(\Delta \hat{c}_j - t(r))]} \quad (16)$$

$$P_j^- = \frac{1}{1 + \exp[-s(-\Delta \hat{c}_j - t(r))]} \quad (17)$$

where s is the steepness parameter and $t(r)$ is the threshold function defined as

$$t(r) = \tau_0 + \tau_1 r^2 + \tau_2 r^4 + \tau_3 r^6 + \tau_4 r^8 \quad (18)$$

with $(\tau_0, \tau_1, \tau_2, \tau_3, \tau_4) \in \mathbb{R}$. For each photon $j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$, random numbers $\hat{u}_j, \hat{v}_j \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 1)$ are sampled to determine the measurement outcome

$$d_j = \begin{cases} +, & \text{if } P_j^+ > \hat{u}_j \text{ and } P_j^- \leq \hat{v}_j \\ -, & \text{if } P_j^+ \leq \hat{u}_j \text{ and } P_j^- > \hat{v}_j \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

where $d_j = +$ indicates detection in the “+” channel, $d_j = -$ indicates detection in the “-” channel, and $d_j = 0$ indicates no detection, while \hat{u}_j and \hat{v}_j model the noise resulting from experimental imperfections.

Coincidences are recorded by comparing the detection outcomes. The single detection efficiencies η_1 , η_2 , and η_3 are determined by the mechanism described above. The correlation function $E_{\text{GHZ}}(\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta}, \hat{\gamma})$ for measurement angles $\hat{\alpha}$, $\hat{\beta}$, and $\hat{\gamma}$ is calculated from the coincidence statistics

$$E_{\text{GHZ}}(\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta}, \hat{\gamma}) = \frac{N_{+++} + N_{+--} + N_{-+-} + N_{--+} + N_{++-} + N_{+-+} + N_{-++} + N_{---}}{N_{\text{total}}} \quad (20)$$

where N_{ijk} represents the number of coincidences with outcome i at the first analyzer, j at the second analyzer, and k at the third analyzer, and $N_{\text{total}} = \sum_{i,j,k \in \{+,-\}} N_{ijk}$.

The value of the parameter function M_3 is calculated using the Mermin inequality [10]

$$M_3 = |E(a', b, c) + E(a, b', c) + E(a, b, c') - E(a', b', c')| \leq 2, \quad (21)$$

and the value of the parameter function S_3 is calculated using the Svetlichny inequality [6]

$$S_3 = |E(a, b, c) + E(a, b, c') + E(a, b', c) - E(a, b', c') + E(a', b, c) - E(a', b, c') - E(a', b', c) - E(a', b', c')| \leq 4 \quad (22)$$

Under local realism $M_3 \leq 2$, while models allowing arbitrary correlations within bipartitions satisfy $S_3 \leq 4$. Quantum mechanics predicts maximum violations $M_3 = 4$ and $S_3 = 4\sqrt{2}$ for pure maximally entangled GHZ states.

The detection probability depends on the measurement settings $\{\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta}, \hat{\gamma}\}$ through the correlation functions E_{GHZ} in Eqs. (6)–(11). Since the random numbers u_i , v_i , and z_i filter different subsets of hidden-variable components depending on the measurement angles, the average detection efficiency $\langle \eta(\hat{\alpha}) \rangle$ (or $\langle \eta(\hat{\beta}) \rangle$, $\langle \eta(\hat{\gamma}) \rangle$) is setting-dependent

$$\langle \eta(\hat{\alpha}) \rangle = \mathbb{E}_{\lambda, U}[P(\lambda, \hat{\alpha}, U)] \quad (23)$$

where $\mathbb{E}_{\lambda, U}$ denotes the expectation value over hidden variables λ and the random samples $U = \{u_i\}_{i=1}^n$, and $P(\lambda, \hat{\alpha}, U)$ is the detection probability defined in Eqs. (16)–(17).

This mechanism violates the setting-independent detection-efficiency assumption, which requires that detection efficiencies be independent of polarizer orientations.

III. Threshold Calibration

The coefficients of the threshold function $t(r)$ were determined using a leave-one-out cross-validation procedure for the state $|\text{GHZ}_r\rangle$, ensuring generalization across different polarizer configurations.

For $r \in \{0.0, 0.1, 0.2, \dots, 1.0\}$, 15 independent optimization iterations were performed, each employing seven randomly generated polarizer configurations with angles uniformly sampled from $[0, 2\pi]$ for the three measurement stations.

Within each iteration, seven-fold leave-one-out cross-validation was applied: six configurations served as the training set for threshold optimization while the seventh was reserved for independent validation. This process cycled through all possible train/test partitions, yielding independent threshold estimates for each r value.

The optimization procedure used grid search over the threshold range $[0.001, 0.800]$ with 40 equally-spaced evaluation points to minimize the multi-objective function:

$$F(t') = |\eta_1(t') - \eta_0| + |\eta_2(t') - \eta_0| + |\eta_3(t') - \eta_0| + p_1 \cdot \max(0, \max_{i,j} |\eta_i(t') - \eta_j(t')| - p_2) + p_3 \cdot |M(t') - M_q| \quad (24)$$

where $\eta_i(t')$ represents the detection efficiency of the i -th detector at threshold t' ($i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ for the three stations), $\eta_0 = 0.73$ is the target efficiency representing a trade-off between detection efficiency and Svetlichny parameter magnitude, and $M(t')$ and M_q are the measured and quantum mechanical predictions of the Mermin parameter M_3 , respectively, given r and the considered polarizers' configuration.

The multi-objective function optimizes three objectives: the terms $|\eta_i(t') - \eta_0|$ constrain all three detector efficiencies to the target value η_0 , $p_3 \cdot |M(t') - M_q|$ maintains the Mermin parameter close to quantum mechanical predictions, and $p_1 \cdot \max(0, \max_{i,j} |\eta_i(t') - \eta_j(t')| - p_2)$ prevents large detection efficiency imbalances among the three detectors. The regularization parameters were set to $p_1 = 2.0$, $p_2 = 0.024$, and $p_3 = 0.1$.

For each threshold evaluation, the multi-objective function was estimated through Monte Carlo simulation of 2000 GHZ triplets per configuration, averaged over three independent runs for statistical stability. Each photon triplet was subjected to linear polarization measurements at randomly selected angle combinations from the current configuration set, with outcomes determined using the detection mechanism described above, including hidden variables $(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3)$ with $n = 21$ components.

Cross-validation yielded 15 iterations for all r values. The standard deviation of thresholds across validation folds was $\sigma_t = 0.0051 \pm 0.0028$. Detection efficiencies on held-out configurations achieved $\eta_1 = 0.728 \pm 0.009$, $\eta_2 = 0.729 \pm 0.009$, and $\eta_3 = 0.728 \pm 0.011$ across the parameter range.

Fitting to Eq. 18 yielded optimal parameters $\tau_0 = 0.0809$, $\tau_1 = 1.9060$, $\tau_2 = -2.7913$, $\tau_3 = 2.4816$, and $\tau_4 = -0.9800$, with RMSE = 0.0036 and $R^2 = 0.9997$.

The empirical determination of these parameters serves as a detector-characterization step, where the fitted values model features—such as threshold sensitivity,

saturation behavior, and noise levels—that in real experiments would be inferred from detector calibration rather than corresponding to physical properties of the apparatus.

IV. Model's Parameters

The Gaussian distribution $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_G^2)$ is used to model the hidden-variable states. The standard deviation $\sigma_G(r) = |1 - r^2|/(\sqrt{3}(1 + r^2))$ determines the dispersion of the hidden-variable distribution, which decreases with the entanglement parameter $|r|$, reaching zero for maximally entangled states.

The parameter n specifies the number of hidden-variable components contributing to the cumulative score, providing the statistical granularity of the sigmoid-based detection mechanism.

The asymmetry of the nonmaximally entangled state $|\text{GHZ}_r\rangle$ is quantified by $|1 - r^2|/(1 + r^2)$, which parametrizes the imbalance between the two components of their superposition.

The factor $1/\sqrt{3}$ ensures that the hidden-variable distribution $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_G^2)$ produces the same statistical dispersion as uniform noise with imbalance $|1 - r^2|/(1 + r^2)$, since $\text{Var}[\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2)] = \text{Var}[\mathcal{U}(-a, a)]$ when $\sigma = a/\sqrt{3}$.

The terms $(1 \pm E_{\text{GHZ}}(\rho, \lambda_j^{(i)}, \lambda_k^{(i)}, r))$ in Eqs. (6)–(11) weight each sample's contribution to the cumulative score.

The sigmoid steepness s determines the sharpness of the detection probability transition in the model.

The threshold function $t(r)$ parametrizes detection sensitivity, affecting the overall detection rate without encoding angular correlations. Its polynomial form exhibits symmetric growth with respect to $|r|$, ensuring bounded threshold values within the sigmoid detection mechanism.

For $|r| \ll 1$, $t(r)$ exhibits approximately quadratic growth from the baseline value τ_0

$$t(r) \approx \tau_0 + \tau_1 r^2 + \mathcal{O}(r^4) \quad (25)$$

The parameter τ_0 sets the baseline threshold at zero entanglement, representing the detection sensitivity floor in the absence of quantum correlations.

This mechanism models polarization-dependent photodetection by accumulating orientation-dependent signal contributions before evaluating the detection outcome. The sigmoid-based detection probabilities P_j^+ and P_j^- in Eqs. (16)–(17) model the competition between the two measurement channels, where $\Delta\hat{c}_1 = (\hat{c}_1^+ - \hat{c}_1^-)$, $\Delta\hat{c}_2 = (\hat{c}_2^+ - \hat{c}_2^-)$ and $\Delta\hat{c}_3 = (\hat{c}_3^+ - \hat{c}_3^-)$ represent the local discrimination signals for the first, second and third photon, respectively. All parameters described above act locally, modulating detection behavior at each station, and do not encode joint or nonlocal dependencies.

The model is not intended to be a full physical description of the detection process, but as an effective framework for examining detection mechanisms and for exploring the conditions under which they approximate quantum correlations.

V. Results

Simulation results are reported in Tables I–II. The configuration used in the first setup is $\alpha = (0^\circ, 90^\circ)$, $\beta = (0^\circ, 90^\circ)$, $\gamma = (-90^\circ, 0^\circ)$, $n = 21$, $s = 20$, $\tau_0 = 0.0809$, $\tau_1 = 1.9060$, $\tau_2 = -2.7913$, $\tau_3 = 2.4816$, and $\tau_4 = -0.9800$. The configuration used in the second setup is $\alpha = (0^\circ, 90^\circ)$, $\beta = (0^\circ, 90^\circ)$, $\gamma = (-45^\circ, 45^\circ)$, $n = 21$, $s = 20$, $\tau_0 = 0.0809$, $\tau_1 = 1.9060$, $\tau_2 = -2.7913$, $\tau_3 = 2.4816$, and $\tau_4 = -0.9800$. Relevant metrics include the Mermin and Svetlichny parameters, and their standard errors; the single detection efficiencies (η_1, η_2, η_3) and their standard errors; the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) between the model's correlations $\hat{E}_{\text{GHZ},r}$ and those predicted by quantum mechanics $E_{\text{GHZ},r}$ for the polarizers' orientations, and its standard error. All quantities are estimated from 100 independent simulations, each using 10^5 triplets of entangled photons. The first and second configurations are optimized to maximize the violation of the Mermin and Svetlichny inequalities respectively.

The Mersenne Twister algorithm is used for all random number generation (i.e., angle selection, cumulative scoring and detection mechanism), ensuring a long period ($2^{19937} - 1$) and high-quality statistical properties.

For the first configuration, the Mermin parameter $|M_3|$ ranges from 0.4755 ± 0.0031 at $r = -0.1$ to a maximum of 3.6991 ± 0.0011 at $r = 0.9$. The Mermin parameter $M_3 = 3.6959 \pm 0.0011$ at $r = 1.0$ exceeds the bound of $M = 2$ by approximately 1592σ . The Svetlichny parameter $|S_3|$ ranges from 0.4787 ± 0.0038 at $r = -0.1$ to 3.6995 ± 0.0032 at $r = -1.0$.

For the second configuration, the Mermin parameter $|M_3|$ ranges from 0.3373 ± 0.0028 at $r = -0.1$ to 2.7203 ± 0.0022 at $r = -0.9$, while the Svetlichny parameter $|S_3|$ ranges from 0.6748 ± 0.0044 at $r = -0.1$ to 5.4417 ± 0.0030 at $r = -0.9$. The Svetlichny parameter $S_3 = 5.4210 \pm 0.0033$ at $r = 1.0$ exceeds the bound of $S_3 = 4$ by approximately 436σ .

For both configurations, the single detection efficiencies range from approximately 72% to approximately 73%. For the first configuration, the RMSE ranges from 0.0164 ± 0.0003 at $r = 0.5$ to 0.0576 ± 0.0005 at $r = -0.1$. For the second configuration, the RMSE ranges from 0.0133 ± 0.0003 at $r = -0.7$ to 0.0569 ± 0.0005 at $r = 0.1$.

VI. Conclusions

This work introduces a local hidden-variable model for tripartite GHZ states. The sigmoid-based threshold mechanism exploits the detection loophole through setting-dependent efficiency, achieving single-detection efficiencies of $\eta \approx 73\%$ for the maximally entangled GHZ state and violating both the Mermin and Svetlichny inequalities. This work explores which structural features affect the model's proximity to quantum predictions and which ones do not. The results show how a local detection mechanism influences Bell inequality tests and how the behaviors produced by the model explored here differ from the experimental findings.

TABLE I. Mermin parameter M_3 , Svetlichny parameter S_3 , single detection efficiencies η_1, η_2, η_3 , and $\text{RMSE}(\hat{E}_{\text{GHZ}_r}, E_{\text{GHZ}_r})$, $\alpha = (0^\circ, 90^\circ)$, $\beta = (0^\circ, 90^\circ)$, $\gamma = (-90^\circ, 0^\circ)$.

r	Mermin M_3	Svetlichny S_3	η_1 (%)	η_2 (%)	η_3 (%)	RMSE
0.1	0.4781 ± 0.0028	0.4800 ± 0.0043	71.7292 ± 0.0133	71.7201 ± 0.0151	71.7147 ± 0.0138	0.0573 ± 0.0005
0.2	1.6799 ± 0.0023	1.6818 ± 0.0038	72.8168 ± 0.0164	72.8056 ± 0.0149	72.8231 ± 0.0127	0.0280 ± 0.0004
0.3	2.4832 ± 0.0019	2.4826 ± 0.0031	73.4923 ± 0.0133	73.5051 ± 0.0129	73.4981 ± 0.0140	0.0511 ± 0.0003
0.4	2.9652 ± 0.0021	2.9656 ± 0.0036	73.2929 ± 0.0156	73.3032 ± 0.0135	73.2759 ± 0.0148	0.0383 ± 0.0004
0.5	3.2665 ± 0.0016	3.2609 ± 0.0031	72.9307 ± 0.0146	72.9279 ± 0.0141	72.9373 ± 0.0134	0.0164 ± 0.0003
0.6	3.4517 ± 0.0017	3.4550 ± 0.0037	72.9254 ± 0.0135	72.9113 ± 0.0140	72.8856 ± 0.0126	0.0180 ± 0.0003
0.7	3.5631 ± 0.0012	3.5605 ± 0.0028	73.1755 ± 0.0136	73.2167 ± 0.0128	73.1973 ± 0.0131	0.0362 ± 0.0002
0.8	3.6374 ± 0.0011	3.6333 ± 0.0030	73.2555 ± 0.0147	73.2203 ± 0.0158	73.2419 ± 0.0134	0.0481 ± 0.0002
0.9	3.6991 ± 0.0011	3.6965 ± 0.0030	72.8455 ± 0.0137	72.8036 ± 0.0133	72.7962 ± 0.0127	0.0504 ± 0.0002
1.0	3.6959 ± 0.0011	3.6911 ± 0.0033	73.1745 ± 0.0154	73.1695 ± 0.0143	73.1713 ± 0.0140	0.0549 ± 0.0002
-0.1	-0.4755 ± 0.0031	-0.4787 ± 0.0038	71.7083 ± 0.0133	71.7235 ± 0.0133	71.7178 ± 0.0151	0.0576 ± 0.0005
-0.2	-1.6815 ± 0.0022	-1.6794 ± 0.0034	72.7866 ± 0.0151	72.8376 ± 0.0124	72.8158 ± 0.0128	0.0285 ± 0.0004
-0.3	-2.4801 ± 0.0019	-2.4763 ± 0.0029	73.4615 ± 0.0137	73.4860 ± 0.0153	73.4781 ± 0.0139	0.0506 ± 0.0003
-0.4	-2.9664 ± 0.0019	-2.9640 ± 0.0029	73.3147 ± 0.0131	73.2875 ± 0.0145	73.2850 ± 0.0147	0.0384 ± 0.0003
-0.5	-3.2705 ± 0.0015	-3.2699 ± 0.0035	72.9058 ± 0.0144	72.9028 ± 0.0150	72.9402 ± 0.0146	0.0168 ± 0.0003
-0.6	-3.4528 ± 0.0015	-3.4540 ± 0.0037	72.9035 ± 0.0142	72.9141 ± 0.0136	72.9435 ± 0.0133	0.0178 ± 0.0003
-0.7	-3.5620 ± 0.0012	-3.5606 ± 0.0031	73.1826 ± 0.0145	73.1870 ± 0.0141	73.2118 ± 0.0149	0.0363 ± 0.0002
-0.8	-3.6392 ± 0.0011	-3.6440 ± 0.0029	73.2250 ± 0.0141	73.2549 ± 0.0136	73.2349 ± 0.0142	0.0477 ± 0.0002
-0.9	-3.6970 ± 0.0012	-3.6982 ± 0.0032	72.7962 ± 0.0160	72.8011 ± 0.0122	72.8247 ± 0.0147	0.0509 ± 0.0002
-1.0	-3.6976 ± 0.0012	-3.6995 ± 0.0032	73.1698 ± 0.0136	73.1768 ± 0.0141	73.1639 ± 0.0147	0.0546 ± 0.0002

TABLE II. Mermin parameter M_3 , Svetlichny parameter S_3 , single detection efficiencies η_1, η_2, η_3 , and $\text{RMSE}(\hat{E}_{\text{GHZ}_r}, E_{\text{GHZ}_r})$, $\alpha = (0^\circ, 90^\circ)$, $\beta = (0^\circ, 90^\circ)$, $\gamma = (-45^\circ, 45^\circ)$.

r	Mermin M_3	Svetlichny S_3	η_1 (%)	η_2 (%)	η_3 (%)	RMSE
0.1	0.3390 ± 0.0027	0.6788 ± 0.0039	71.7292 ± 0.0133	71.7201 ± 0.0151	71.7368 ± 0.0137	0.0569 ± 0.0005
0.2	1.1874 ± 0.0028	2.3815 ± 0.0039	72.8168 ± 0.0164	72.8056 ± 0.0149	72.8253 ± 0.0140	0.0286 ± 0.0005
0.3	1.7712 ± 0.0023	3.5436 ± 0.0034	73.4923 ± 0.0133	73.5051 ± 0.0129	73.4912 ± 0.0156	0.0550 ± 0.0004
0.4	2.1417 ± 0.0024	4.2906 ± 0.0032	73.2929 ± 0.0156	73.3032 ± 0.0135	73.2945 ± 0.0147	0.0499 ± 0.0004
0.5	2.3913 ± 0.0023	4.7798 ± 0.0032	72.9307 ± 0.0146	72.9279 ± 0.0141	72.9257 ± 0.0148	0.0335 ± 0.0004
0.6	2.5397 ± 0.0020	5.0810 ± 0.0030	72.9254 ± 0.0135	72.9113 ± 0.0140	72.9111 ± 0.0139	0.0153 ± 0.0003
0.7	2.6227 ± 0.0020	5.2421 ± 0.0027	73.1755 ± 0.0136	73.2167 ± 0.0128	73.1992 ± 0.0146	0.0135 ± 0.0003
0.8	2.6717 ± 0.0020	5.3453 ± 0.0026	73.2555 ± 0.0147	73.2203 ± 0.0158	73.2245 ± 0.0136	0.0237 ± 0.0003
0.9	2.7210 ± 0.0019	5.4408 ± 0.0029	72.8455 ± 0.0137	72.8036 ± 0.0133	72.7981 ± 0.0151	0.0251 ± 0.0003
1.0	2.7107 ± 0.0021	5.4210 ± 0.0033	73.1745 ± 0.0154	73.1695 ± 0.0143	73.1469 ± 0.0131	0.0310 ± 0.0004
-0.1	-0.3373 ± 0.0028	-0.6748 ± 0.0044	71.7083 ± 0.0133	71.7235 ± 0.0133	71.7314 ± 0.0148	0.0574 ± 0.0005
-0.2	-1.1904 ± 0.0026	-2.3782 ± 0.0038	72.7866 ± 0.0151	72.8376 ± 0.0124	72.8127 ± 0.0145	0.0283 ± 0.0005
-0.3	-1.7703 ± 0.0024	-3.5427 ± 0.0036	73.4615 ± 0.0137	73.4860 ± 0.0153	73.4719 ± 0.0133	0.0550 ± 0.0004
-0.4	-2.1451 ± 0.0022	-4.2871 ± 0.0029	73.3147 ± 0.0131	73.2875 ± 0.0145	73.2556 ± 0.0153	0.0495 ± 0.0004
-0.5	-2.3916 ± 0.0022	-4.7806 ± 0.0032	72.9058 ± 0.0144	72.9028 ± 0.0150	72.9081 ± 0.0129	0.0337 ± 0.0004
-0.6	-2.5379 ± 0.0022	-5.0789 ± 0.0036	72.9035 ± 0.0142	72.9141 ± 0.0136	72.9240 ± 0.0166	0.0152 ± 0.0004
-0.7	-2.6207 ± 0.0021	-5.2439 ± 0.0027	73.1826 ± 0.0145	73.1870 ± 0.0141	73.1785 ± 0.0140	0.0133 ± 0.0003
-0.8	-2.6733 ± 0.0019	-5.3478 ± 0.0027	73.2250 ± 0.0141	73.2549 ± 0.0136	73.2343 ± 0.0140	0.0236 ± 0.0003
-0.9	-2.7203 ± 0.0022	-5.4417 ± 0.0030	72.7962 ± 0.0160	72.8011 ± 0.0122	72.8078 ± 0.0127	0.0250 ± 0.0004
-1.0	-2.7142 ± 0.0022	-5.4279 ± 0.0030	73.1698 ± 0.0136	73.1768 ± 0.0141	73.1687 ± 0.0131	0.0304 ± 0.0004

- [1] Bell, J. S., On the Einstein Podolsky Rosen paradox, *Physics Physique Fizika* **1**, 195–200 (1964).
- [2] Clauser, J. F., Horne, M. A., Shimony, A., and Holt, R. A., Proposed Experiment to Test Local Hidden-Variable Theories, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **23**, 880–884 (1969).
- [3] D. M. Greenberger, M. A. Horne, and A. Zeilinger, “Going beyond Bell’s theorem,” in *Bell’s Theorem, Quantum Theory, and Conceptions of the Universe*, edited by M. Kafatos (Kluwer Academic, Dordrecht, 1989), pp. 69–72.
- [4] D. M. Greenberger, M. A. Horne, A. Shimony, and A. Zeilinger, Bell’s theorem without inequalities, *Am. J. Phys.* **58**, 1131 (1990).
- [5] J.-W. Pan, D. Bouwmeester, M. Daniell, H. Weinfurter, and A. Zeilinger, Experimental test of quantum nonlocality in three-photon Greenberger-Horne-Zeilinger entanglement, *Nature* **403**, 515 (2000).
- [6] G. Svetlichny, Distinguishing three-body from two-body nonseparability by a Bell-type inequality, *Phys. Rev. D* **35**, 3066 (1987).
- [7] P. M. Pearle, Hidden-variable example based upon data rejection, *Phys. Rev. D* **2**, 1418 (1970).
- [8] A. Cabello, D. Rodríguez, and I. Villanueva, Necessary and sufficient detection efficiency for the Mermin inequalities, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **101**, 120402 (2008).

- [9] D. Bouwmeester, J.-W. Pan, M. Daniell, H. Weinfurter, and A. Zeilinger, Observation of Three-Photon Greenberger-Horne-Zeilinger Entanglement, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **82**, 1345 (1999).
- [10] N. D. Mermin, Extreme quantum entanglement in a superposition of macroscopically distinct states, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **65**, 1838 (1990).
- [11] M. Ardehali, Bell inequalities with a magnitude of violation that grows exponentially with the number of particles, *Phys. Rev. A* **46**, 5375 (1992).
- [12] A. V. Belinskii and D. N. Klyshko, Interference of light and Bell's theorem, *Phys. Usp.* **36**, 653 (1993).
- [13] A. Cabello, Bell's theorem with and without inequalities for the three-qubit Greenberger-Horne-Zeilinger and W states, *Phys. Rev. A* **65**, 032108 (2002).
- [14] Y. Xiang, H.-X. Wang, and F.-Y. Hong, *Detection efficiency in the loophole-free violation of Svetlichny's inequality*, *Phys. Rev. A* **86**, 034102 (2012).
- [15] S. B. Ghosh, S. Roy Chowdhury, R. Adhikary, A. Roy, and T. Guha, *Minimum detection efficiencies for loophole-free genuine nonlocality tests*, *Phys. Rev. A* **109**, 052202 (2024).